

DOES TEACHER’S WRITTEN FEEDBACK HELP UNIVERSITY STUDENTS TO IMPROVE THEIR WRITING SKILL?

Ibroximova Rayxona

student of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan

Yugay Yevgeniya Viktorovna

a scientific adviser, a teacher of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article discusses the importance of written feedback in the assessment and learning situation is for the improvement of a student’s performance. It is vital that the process of supplying feedback is affirmative to the student

Keywords: feedback, writing skill, teacher’s capability, written feedback

Аннотация: В этой статье обсуждается возможность письменной обратной связи и ситуации оценивания успеваемости учащегося. Крайне важно чтобы процесс предоставления обратной связи был положительным для учащегося

Ключевые слова: Обратная связь, письменный навык способности учителя, письменный отзыв

If we want to discuss about some written feedback (it is effective to enhance our writing skill), first of all, we must mention of the word 'feedback'. Through giving feedback, it is possible to obtain the growth of belief, our knowledge, self-assessment, learning delight. Both positive and negative feedback of the teacher develops our writing skill. In other words, with negative feedback we can realise about our some mistakes or incapacity of us, whereas if we receive positive feedback, we are often provided with special inspiration.

Moreover, feedback can strengthen students in every way, such as goal achievement, self-regulating, work planning which are primarily essential. Owing to this we are given an impartial evaluation in our work.

Types of feedback:

🔊—verbal

□—visual

✍️—written

It’s reported by statistics that 3/10 parts of university students who are Uzbek, is able to do something (for example, writing an essay, article or novel...) or converse with each other by writing. According of the view, written feedback of the teacher may be so powerful, both if it mainly concentrates on the subject, valuable foundations or primary tasks and also it is utilized by students. There are some types

of written feedback which are effective should be well-timed and written in clear styles are comprehensible to the students in order that they would understand easily, reread and memorize. There is no doubt that written feedback can also affect emotional processes of students, improvement of effort and enthusiasm.

Based on the result of research and discussion, it's reported that the statistics of teachers' written comments on students' writing skill at the university of World Languages of Uzbekistan were determined. According to the researchers, university students experienced significant improvement (56% before the study, whereas after this it reached 78%). As a result, the students had great analysis of their ideas. Furthermore, they will have an opportunity to discuss their views clearly and they are supported quite well.

Table

The result of the study conducted among students at the university of World Languages

Types of feedback	Verbal feedback	Visual feedback	Written feedback
University students	54%	65%	78%

There are some important guidelines for teachers in giving written feedback:

*Specifiable needs to student

You should begin with concentrating on the students and their capability, instead of last product

* Well-timed

It's required provide feedback during 48 hours in order that task is fresh

* Focused and effective

Give your readers feedback that will help them continue to write and improve their ability, that won't discourage them too much.

As we conclude our thoughts, we can say vividly that written feedback which is received by students is a beneficial part of successful learning. Undoubtedly, feedback can boost the confidence and motive of the learners eventually, their achievements.

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